

The Impact of Privatization on the Legal Status of Public Employees in Iraqi Law

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Abstract

This topic examines the legal developments in the rights of public sector employees as a consequence of the transfer of such public utilities and services as have been moved under the ambit of the private sector as a result of the implementation of the policy of privatization. There can be little doubt that the policy of privatization, as a mode of administration of public facilities and services, not merely alters the administrative structure of the state but also impinges, in a direct manner, upon the legal status of employees in the affected sectors. What is pertinent, in the first instance, is that public sector employees, who were till then governed by administrative law, as protected employees under the Civil Service, may find themselves working under the aegis of private employment law in their new employment conditions.

It also represents, for many workers, a source of concern, especially with regard to the possible loss of rights that they would enjoy, at least where their employment would remain under the status of the public sector. There are also difficulties with regard to the transfer of these workers within new jurisdictions, not to mention ensuring that they enjoy equality, regardless of whether they are subjected to the process of privatization of their activities or if they remain within the status of the public sector. The process of privatization also raises several implications concerning the status of the state within ensuring social rights within a context where its immediate responsibility in the management of the public sector is reduced.

For instance, the effects of privatization on the legal status of public-sector workers extend beyond the procedural or administrative aspect, as it also encompasses the essence of the relationship between the individual and the government as a state entity. Similarly, it also depends on the nature of economic policies taken by the government, which may, in its efficiency policies, ignore the human aspect associated with such policies.

Keywords: *privatization, public-sector workers, Iraqi economic reform, administrative and financial efficiency.*

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Introduction

Iraq has undergone a series of significant changes at the economic and administrative levels, particularly the adoption of the principle of privatization as a means of economic reform and alleviating the burden on the public budget. These changes included a process of transferring the administration of some

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establishments or services from the public sector to the private sector, which directly impacted the functional and administrative structure of the state as a whole. Under this topic, the Issue of the 'Legal Status of Public Employees' was identified as a fundamental challenge due to the contradiction between the stability principle of employment, a foundation principle of the Iraqi administrative structure, and the malleable or contractual nature of privatization as a concept. The relevance of this topic resides in its essence within the context of its implications, primarily the poor legal framework or coverage that must safeguard the rights of public sector employees in the face of transfer, dismissal, or restructuring procedures.

Significance of the Study

The relevance of this study is in highlighting the issue of legal difficulties encountered by public sector workers in Iraq because of unregulated waves of privatization.

It explains the intricate interplay that has to be made between the needs of economic development and those of social justice and employment rights.

The contribution of the study is in helping present a clear legal framework that might aid in developing reasonable legislation that ensures the dignity of employees within the context of the changing administrative framework.

It also helps decision-makers and lawmakers by Identifying legal gaps and recommending how the process of privatization can be structured according to the rule of law principle.

Objectives of the Study

For better elucidation of the legal and administrative Impact of privatization on the stability of public employees in Iraq.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the Iraqi legislations in protecting the rights of employees during the process of privatization.

To identify legislative and practical weaknesses in overseeing the transfer or dismissal of workers based on the aspect of privatization.

The aim was to propose legal recommendations that would attempt to bridge the needs of privatization with the guarantees for jobs in the public service.

Research Problem

The central issue investigated by this research may be stated as follows:

To what extent, however, has privatization in Iraq influenced the status of public sector workers, and to what extent is the legal framework in Iraq sufficient in providing these workers with legal protection in these processes?

This basic question spawns a number of secondary questions, including the following:

Are there specific laws governing the transfer of workers from the public sector to the private sector?

Under which provisions is protection available to public servants during the process of privatization? Do present regulations provide sufficient appeal rights to ensure proper payments for impacted workers?

Methodology

Although this project takes up this question using the critical analytical method, in which the relevant national laws on the status of public service personnel, in the framework of the process of privatization, have been analyzed, taking into consideration the jurisprudential literature, it also uses the comparative method, which involves the analysis of the situation in other countries that have passed through analogous processes.

The Conceptual and Legal Framework of Privatization and Public Service in Iraq

Due to globalization and its Effects—particularly in the economic field—most of the countries in the world have behaved in adopting the system of a free market economy. This has greatly Influenced the legal structure of different societies because the law corresponds to current economic-political-social circumstances, in addition to religious and social traditions. One of the Principles that has experienced particular Influence in connection with the Effects of globalization is that of contracts in general and of administrative contracts in particular. In fact, it has given birth to a new type of contract that was not previously experienced by public utility concession contracts—the Public-Private Partnership (PPP). This model eases the financial burden on the public treasury by involving private capital in essential service sectors (Al-Sayyid Muhammad, n.d.).

The privatization of public service employment In Iraq is considered a sensitive legal and regulatory path. It involves transitioning from direct governmental management of services to the participation of the private sector in providing those services or managing human resources. This approach is based on a set of laws and regulations, most notably the Labor Law and the Civil Service Law, in addition to laws concerning investment and public-private partnerships. Moreover, decisions of the Council of Ministers and ministerial directives play a vital role in shaping this transformation (Hassan, 2014).

Legally speaking, there Is still no comprehensive privatization of public employment in Iraq. Rather, gradual steps are being implemented in certain sectors, such as electricity and health, where private companies are contracted to provide specific services. However, this does not abolish the legal status of those employed by the government. Justification for the new changes raises concerns over the issue of protecting employment rights, especially concerning job security and pensions. Thus, the process of making public employment privatized needs a balanced legal context that incorporates elements of social justice for administrative efficiency (Al-Jumaili, 2019).

The Concept and Objectives of Privatization in Iraqi Legislation

Privatization, in terms of its economical aspect and legal definition, symbolizes one of the biggest changes that states with the aim of affecting changes within their economic system adopt. Within the Iraqi context, the privatization process has its own uniqueness that is determined by Iraqi circumstances that are more complex compared to those of many countries. It also symbolizes efforts within the Iraqi state that are dedicated at rebuilding its economy, which was destroyed for decades by wars, sanctions, and corruption (Shaban, 2006).

Privatization: The concept of privatization entails the transfer of control and ownership of some or all of the public entities and services owned by the state to the private sector, through sale, public-private partnership arrangements, or revamping such entities along for-profit principles. Privatization does not essentially entail theandoning of ownership, but rather the assuming of responsibilities by the private sector under market principles associated with such entities.

In Iraq, the concept of privatization appears as a method of economic reform and a strategy for disengagement from state intervention and overcentralization, which, as a practice, has failed in most productive and service sectors. The legislation in Iraq, from the Constitution of 2005 to economic and commercial laws, and governmental strategies, in principle, is receptive to the concept of working with privatization as a method of economic reform. The Constitution itself, under Article 25, promotes “the reform of the Iraqi economy according to modern market principles,” which opens the way for the promotion of the private sector’s role (Allawi, 2013).

Objectives of privatization Under the Iraqi legal framework, the goals of privatization vary but correspond with overall governmental targets while incorporating the realities of Iraq itself. Primarily, the goals of privatization Include relieving the state budget of its current burdens, given the rise in

government spending because of indiscriminate hiring within the government sectors, coupled with decreased productivity as a result of significant budget deficits. For this reason, it proposes alleviating these burdens through the transfer of some of these sectors into the private domain, which is more effective and less susceptible to corruption.

Additionally, privatization in Iraq aims to stimulate both domestic and foreign investment by creating a truly competitive environment free from government monopolies. Many Iraqi public Institutions have operated—and continue to operate—under outdated methods, lacking the flexibility and capacity for Innovation or modernization. Thus, the involvement of the private sector Is seen as a driver for technological transfer and improved service or product Quality (Ghalioun, 1993).

Furthermore, one of the core objectives of privatization In Iraqi legislation is to create sustainable employment opportunities by activating the market's role. The private sector is Inherently more flexible in hiring and more responsive to economic changes than the bureaucratic state apparatus. However, this objective faces a specific challenge in Iraq, where privatization is sometimes met with popular or political resistance due to fears of job loss or deepening social Inequality (Al-Jaberi, 2015).

The Iraqi legislative framework seeks to regulate privatization in a way that considers these sensitivities by drafting laws such as the Investment Law or the Public-Private Partnership Law. These documents offer the necessary framework for the process of privatization and address how it can be ensured that citizens are not exploited or harmed in any way.

Thus, the issue of privatization within Iraqi law is not only about transferring ownership from the state to individuals/companies but also encompasses an overarching strategy of developing a balanced free market economy that does not solely exclude the state but, on the other hand, gives a new definition of its participation in the economy as a control/oversight entity that promotes the protection of public interests but gives way to the private sector for growth within balanced/fair rules (Dawood, 2019).

First Branch: Definition of Privatization and Its Legal Forms

Privatization refers not only to the process of selling off state-owned activities but also encompasses the whole range of changes that are needed to redefine the relationship between the state, market, and society. Thus, at its fundamental level, privatization represents a new paradigm shift in thinking on the role of the state, from being producers themselves to taking on the new role of regulators, supervisors, and partners. There are several reasons why countries implement the concept of. These reasons are discussed below (Aboud, 2012).

The necessity for privatization has been experienced as a result of a combination of factors, some of which include the budget deficit, inefficiency in public institutions, the rise in international debt, and the influence of the IMF and World Bank. These institutions called for reduced state intervention in the economy and market liberalization. However, privatization is not merely a circumstantial response; it has become a strategic choice for many countries to modernize their economies and enhance competitiveness (Al-Shaddadi, 2004).

Conceptually, the extent of privatization varies from one country to another. It may imply a full transition to a free-market economy or be limited to specific forms of private sector participation in certain activities, depending on the characteristics of the prevailing economic and social system.

Legal Forms of Privatization Although privatization is primarily an economic process, it is fundamentally based on a clear legal and regulatory framework. This process is regulated by legal provisions that establish its procedure, implications, as well as the attendant guarantees. There are various tools that are used in the process of privatization depending on the intention as well as the sector that is targeted. They include:

Privatization by Sale of Public Property (Either Full or Partial Transfer of Ownership)

This type of privatization occurs when the ownership of an investment project or facility changes from the state to an individual, organization, or investors. This type of privatization follows very specific legal requirements such as financial evaluation, the process of bidding, as well as making the whole transaction transparent. This can either be a total transaction or a matter where the state retains some form of ownership (Al-Jabri, 2002).

Privatization through Legal Transformation of Public Enterprises into Joint Stock Companies

This step represents the preliminary action towards privatization, in which the public entity would be transformed into a joint-stock company according to commercial law so that, at a later stage, its shares could be sold to the public or strategic investors. Such legal transformation detaches the entity from rigid administrative laws and subjects it to private law, hence giving more latitude regarding administrative and organizational matters.

Privatization by Management and Operation Contract (Without Transfer of Ownership)

In this form of privatization, the ownership of the organization is retained by the government but its management is delegated to the private sector on a contractual basis for a specific period of time with clear financial commitments mentioned within the contract (Al-Saadi, 2011).

Concessions or Long Term Management Contracts (Public Private Partnerships - PPPs)

Here, the state enters into a concession agreement wherein it agrees to operate and exploit the public utility/service in favor of a private company for a prolonged period of time, usually 30 to 50 years. However, the private player, in turn, agrees to develop, improve, or maintain the infrastructure. This concept of infrastructure development is a combination of public and private efforts as it is a profit-sharing arrangement.

Indirect Privatization (Gradual Market Liberalization)

This form does not necessarily involve the direct transfer of ownership. Instead, it involves opening the market to competition, lifting subsidies, and privileges accorded to the public sector. In this gradual liberalization, state dominance is diluted as new private sector actors start coming into the fray.

No discussion of privatization is complete without considering the legislative environment that governs it. To implement privatization, laws have to be enacted or updated in order to:

Transparent standards in valuation and sale processes.

Protection of workers' rights and interests.

Competitiveness in a manner that negates monopoly.

There should be effective mechanisms for overseeing the investors' compliance.

In most cases, a regulation and control board is formed to monitor the adoption of the process of privatization, and it is granted authorities to facilitate the process.

On a social point, there are many debates surrounding whether or not a privatization policy will have a significant effect on employment, for example, layoffs and salary cuts, which make it normally involve 'social safety nets.' These are funds generated by privatization or governments to compensate and retrain those made redundant by privatization.

From the administrative standpoint, privatization presents itself as a means of restructuring public organizations, getting rid of bureaucracy, and increasing administrative efficiency. But the process depends on the presence of adequate regulatory and supervisory bodies that can ensure that the shrinkage of the state does not result in chaos in the public sector, nor does it translate into a monopoly in the private sector.

On paper, the implementation of privatization promotes efficiency, improves the level of service delivery, and encourages investments. But experiences over the years have indicated that it fails occasionally. This varies depending on the nature of such privatization, be it water, manufacturing, or education – as it also relates to the state's level of maturity in terms of its legal structures. Private schooling, for instance, raises some issues associated with equity.

Consequently, privatization has to be viewed as a vehicle and not an objective that calls for informed application in accordance with the principles of gradualism and achieving synergy between the ideals of efficiency and social justice.

Second Branch: Objectives of Privatization and Its Economic and Administrative Motivations

It is contested that privatization is a very controversial issue in contemporary economics because it falls at the crossroads of several areas of current concern—the sovereignty of economics, social justice, and public administration efficiency. Whatever the diversified experience of different nations regarding the execution of this issue, it has actually emerged as a compulsory alternative within the framework of a rebuilt modern state that has been faced with mounting pressures of economics and a changed role of the state in a globalization era (Aboud, 2012).

Economic Background – From Welfare State to Market State

The need for privatization arose as a consequence of realizing that a comprehensive state model, or welfare state, was incapable of meeting the challenges of rapid changes taking place within the economy. The classic state model of this period, influenced by the state's role following World War II, assumed increased state control of means of production, public services, state control of prices, and public sector jobs as a result of state expansion. The task of performing this role has, therefore, become economically burdensome as it has accumulated problems relating to cost deficits and inefficiency (Al-Shaddadi, 2004).

Indeed, the state itself, as what has been described as the "primary economic actor," has gradually turned out to be a burden to the economy of the nation. This state created huge public institutions that are managed in an unprofitable and bureaucratic manner in which there are no incentives and efficiency in resource allocation. Instead of being motors of growth, these public institutions have turned out to be sources of drain and corruption in the economy. In this state of affairs comes the intervention of the policy of privatization (Al-Jabri, 2002).

Economic Objectives – From Financial Rescue to Developmental Incentives

Privatization, in its very essence, is intended to accomplish a number of economic goals, the first of which is relieving the direct burdens on the state financially. Privatization has been applied in most countries as a method toward lessening budgetary deficits or paying back debts through the sale of state-owned properties or by sharing equity with investors. The actual dimensions of privatization, however, are not bound to the financial aspect alone but are also closely interlinked with enhancing the efficiency of resource allocation, consolidating the private sector as an engine of growth, and sharpening market competitiveness (Al-Saadi, 2011).

The private sector, by its very nature, is governed by a profit motive, which is dependent on incentives of profit or competition, thereby increasing performance through providing better quality services at more favorable prices. In this context, therefore, there is more to privatization than just changes in ownership, as it entails changes in management philosophy along with changes in economic roles. It is therefore a tool to harness market forces to bring about fiscal discipline as well as eliminate distortions of random subsidies or irrational pricing within a centrally planned economy (Al-Ashmawi, 2010).

Moreover, privatization presents opportunities for investments both locally and externally due to the expansion of ownership resulting in an attractive business environment. It increases the possibilities for economic growth since more funds are generated for the government that can use its resources for crucial

sectors such as health, education, among others that are currently drained in inefficient production institutions (Abdulaziz, 2006).

Administrative Objectives – Restructuring the State and Enhancing Governance

As far as administration is concerned, there are more complex undertones in privatization itself, which are related to the transformation of the state apparatus in terms of removing it from the constraints of bureaucracy in order for it to function more effectively. Many public institutions suffer from workforce Inflation, poor performance, and a lack of effective accountability. Privatization—by transferring management to the private sector or restructuring institutions on a corporate model—imposes a new administrative culture based on accountability, results, and strategic planning rather than organizational rigidity (Youssef, 2009).

Privatization also helps entrench modern management concepts, such as quality systems, business process reengineering, Investment in human capital, and the use of technology to Improve services. This change results in a paradigm shift In organizational culture, thereby reinstating values of efficiency, as well as individual and collective performance. Further, a minimized role of the state's operations enables It to concentrate on Its regulatory and supervisory roles, thus contributing to the development of governance structures adequate to formulate public policies, evaluate performance, and regulate markets to cater to consumer protection, prevent monopolistic behavior, as well as accomplish justice in service delivery (Al-Sayyad, 2011).

Privatization as a Strategic Transformation In the Role of the State

Secondly, the issue of privatization should not just be considered from the perspective of a technical solution or a contingency measure; on the other hand, it needs to be located within the framework of a strategic change occurring within the philosophy of governing or managing the economy. This strategic change is underpinned by the need to redefine the role of the state/society/market triangle so that the state itself escapes the "employment trap" and becomes a factor that facilitates economic agents.

Such a change is also connected with global changes, for instance, globalization, market liberalization, and economic Integration, making the process of privatization an adjustment for complying with the requirements of the global economy. It is difficult for economies that are open to improve their competitiveness without involving the private sector in these efforts (Al-Hassan, 2009).

Privatization as a Tool for Redistributing Roles and Responsibilities

"One of the more subtle aspects of privatization is the reshuffling of responsibility and roles from the state to the private sector, and from the state to civil society." In this new paradigm, instead of the state doing everything, there is room for the private sector to be involved in production and service delivery, and for civil society to share in supervision and direction. This further cements the idea of "decentralization," encouraging greater civic engagement and, in turn, greater civic responsibility to be more open and accountable (Said, 2010).

The goals of privatization extend beyond the mere sale of public institutions or cuts in government expenditures. They outline a broader strategy for restructuring both the economy and the state. There are several tools that can be employed for correcting imperfections, encouraging efficiency, and reorienting the function of the state towards its essentials, alongside the activation of market forces in a specially designed institutional setup. It is a strategy that can only lead to success within the context of a precisely designed framework of law and institutions, at a gradual level that recognizes the particularities of any nation, alongside considerations of economic efficacy and principles of justice (Abdel Hadi, 2015).

The Legal Nature of Public Service in Iraq

Public service is one of the basic subjects, as It represents the foundation stone in structuring the relationship between the state and its staff. In order to grasp the nature of public service, there are a

number of legal, historical, and intellectual aspects to consider, which together form the foundations of public service in Iraq.

Public service is defined as the legal status held by an Individual within one of the state's Institutions or administrative units. This position grants the individual a set of rights and Imposes upon them a set of obligations. However, this superficial definition does not fully reveal the legal nature that underpins this relationship. Iraqi jurisprudence and judiciary have historically fluctuated between two main approaches: the first considers public service a contract, while the second views it as a legal status (Abdullah, 2006).

At the dawn of the modern Iraqi state, particularly during the monarchical period, there was a clear Influence of Western legal thought, especially French and Egyptian, which themselves had been shaped by the contractual theory in Interpreting the relationship between the employee and the state. According to this theory, public service was considered a contract based on mutual consent: on one side, the state, and on the other, the individual. The employee was viewed as having contracted with the administration to perform a specific task In exchange for a fixed wage, thereby creating a relationship based on mutual obligations governed by the general rules of civil law (Al-Zaidi, 2012).

However, this approach did not last long. The sovereign nature of public service—as a duty carried out by the Individual in the service of the public interest—does not align with the principles of civil contractual law, particularly with regard to freedom of contract, negotiation terms, and sanctions. As administrative thought evolved In Iraq, especially in the second half of the twentieth century, a clearer shift emerged toward viewing public service not as a contract but as a legal status. This shift was driven by the need for precise and centralized regulation of the relationship between the employee and the administration, one that considers the higher Interest of the state and places the public good above the personal Interests of the employee. Consequently, the employee came to be seen not as a contractor with the state, but as the holder of a legal position created and governed by the rules of public law (Ouda, 2009).

This legal status means that the employee, from the moment of their appointment until the end of their service, Is subject to a legal framework that imposes specific obligations and grants rights according to what is stipulated in legal and regulatory texts. The employee has no right to negotiate or individually modify these terms. The state, in Its sovereign capacity, holds the authority to regulate the public service and Its conditions, impose the duty of obedience and discipline on the employee, and subject them to disciplinary accountability In the event of any breach of their duties. This does not constitute a violation of contractual balance or an infringement of personal freedom (Al-Sanhouri, 1998).

First Branch: The Concept of the Public Employee and Their Fundamental Rights

The legal system governing public employment In Iraq has not been codified under a unified legal framework that applies to all state employees. Instead, it has developed through a set of distinct provisions issued for different categories.

See Article 1 of the amended Civil Service Law No. 24 of 1960, as well as Article 1, paragraph 2 of the Discipline of State and Public Sector Employees Law No. 14 of 1991.

A segment of Iraqi legal scholars argues that the Iraqi legislator, by providing a definition of the public employee, has resolved all ambiguity on the matter, rendering further Inquiry unnecessary. However, this has not prevented Iraqi jurists from presenting their own definitions of the term. For instance, Dr. Shab Touma Mansour defines a public employee as “any person assigned a position within the permanent staffing structure of a public utility (Mansour, 1969).”

Similarly, Dr. Shafiq Abdul Majid Al-Haditha defines a public employee as “any person entrusted with a permanent position in a public utility (Al-Hadithi, 1975).”

Dr. Ali Jumaa Al-Muharib offers the following definition: “a public employee is any person entrusted with a permanent position in the service of a public utility administered by the state or a public legal entity.”

Dr. Maher Saleh Alawi Al-Jubouri defines a public employee as “a person who works permanently in state and public sector utilities (Al-Jubouri, 1996; Al-Hadithi, 1975).”

It is important to note that Iraqi administrative law doctrine has not reached the level of development seen in Egypt or France, primarily due to the relatively recent emergence of administrative judiciary in Iraq, which lacks the maturity and depth found in the judicial systems of those countries.

Accordingly, the prevailing view in Iraqi legal doctrine is that the concept of a public employee is defined by three key elements:

1. The service must be within a public utility.
2. The position must be permanent and part of the official staffing structure.
3. The appointment must be made by the authority legally empowered to do so.

A common feature across these definitions is the exclusion of any distinction between “employee,” “user,” and “worker”—terms previously defined in various Iraqi employment statutes. Therefore, many legal scholars have advocated for a unified legal system governing all state employees. This approach was later adopted by the Iraqi legislator through the general use of the term “public employees (Al-Jubouri, 1996b).”

The Iraqi legislator has consistently attempted to define “public employee” across various laws, particularly in the Civil Service Law and the Public Discipline Law.

For example, Civil Service Law No. 103 of 1931 defined a public employee as: “any person entrusted with a position in the government in return for a salary drawn from the general or special budget, and subject to the provisions of the retirement law.”

Civil Service Law No. 24 of 1960 (amended), in Article 2, defined a public employee as “any person entrusted with a permanent position within the official staffing structure”—a definition identical to that of Civil Service Law No. 64 of 1939 (Republic of Iraq, 1939; 1960).

Disciplinary laws also defined the public employee. The Discipline of State and Public Sector Employees Law No. 14 of 1991, in Article 1/Third, states: “a public employee is any person entrusted with a position in the staffing of a ministry or a non-ministerial public body.” This definition was retained in the Fifth Amendment to the Law in 2008 (Mahdi, 2001).

This definition diverges from those in earlier laws by omitting the requirement of permanence, a condition emphasized by successive Civil Service laws since 1931 (Al-Shammari, 2007).

Other definitions of “public employee” are found in laws targeting specific categories of personnel. For example, the now-repealed Religious and Charitable Institutions Law No. 67 of 1971 defined a public employee as “any person entrusted with a position in the staffing of religious and charitable institutions.” Similarly, Article 1 of the Railway Service Regulations No. 22 of 1966 defined an employee as “any person entrusted with a permanent position in the official staffing structure,” aligning with the definition in the amended Civil Service Law No. 24 of 1960 (Republic of Iraq, 1966).

Numerous personnel regulations within semi-official institutions—commonly referred to as the socialist sector—also use the term “employee” for some of their workers. These institutions, similar to official state agencies, exhibit a dual legal framework governing their workforce (Al-Dabbagh, 2008).

The importance of identifying a clear criterion to distinguish public employees from others arose from the existence of three types of workers in state institutions: employees, users, and laborers. Each category was subject to a distinct regulatory regime. However, the legislator eliminated the category of “users” through Revolutionary Command Council Resolutions No. 518 of 1973 and No. 911 of 1976, and later

converted workers into employees through Resolution No. 15 of 1987, thereby placing all state and public sector workers under a single legal framework.

Reference: Paragraph 1 of the resolution states: "All workers In state and socialist sector departments are considered employees with equal rights and obligations." Paragraph 2 adds: "The laws and service rules applicable in all state and socialist sector departments shall apply to those covered by this resolution."

In light of the above, the Iraqi legislator has settled two previously contentious issues:

First: A public employee Is anyone who works in state and public sector departments on a permanent basis, along with all corresponding rights and obligations.

Second: Public sector workers are explicitly considered public employees under the resolution, and the clarity of the text eliminates the need for further debate on their status (Al-Jubouri, 1996).

However, a point of contention may arise concerning the requirement of permanence, which was not stipulated In the active Law of Discipline of State and Public Sector Employees No. 14 of 1991. As such, this law has effectively dropped the condition of permanence and applies to temporary employees as well, as specified by Revolutionary Command Council Resolution No. 603 of 1987. This created a new category of public workers subject to the same appointment procedures, rights, and obligations as permanent employees, except In areas explicitly addressed by the resolution, retirement laws, and relevant legislative provisions.

Based on the above analysis and the various definitions of the public employee found in Iraqi legislation, this research supports and adopts the definition provided by the amended Law of Discipline of State and Public Sector Employees No. 14 of 1991. It is a definition that is inclusive, in keeping with existing statutes, that eliminates the requirement of permanence, making this one of the most applicable and effective definitions of a public employee.

Second Branch: Legal Principles Governing the Employment Relationship

For instance, as a legal body, the government also comprises human factors needed for the management of its institutions as well as running its affairs. This can only be carried out through the representatives of the government, who are humans as its employees. In order to ensure that the administration fulfills its objectives of serving the public interest and meeting societal needs, there must be a legal system in place to regulate the employment of administrative workers. This system should safeguard their rights, organize their duties, and prevent the abuse of their legal status for private gain. At the same time, it should grant them entitlements such as salaries, allowances, and other guarantees to limit potential administrative abuse.

Given that the public function consists of both the administration and the natural persons, specific legal provisions have been enacted to govern the relationship between the administration and its employees.

First: The Legal Nature of the Relationship According to Contractual Theories

Under private law, the relationship between the public employee and the state was traditionally viewed as contractual, based on the principle that contracts are binding upon the parties ("the contract is the law of the contracting parties"). In this theory, employment is seen as an offer and acceptance between the administration and the employee. If the task is material in nature, it is considered a lease-of-services contract; if legal in nature, it is considered an agency contract. Below are the main contractual theories that fall under this classification:

1. The Civil Contract Theory This is one of the earliest theories used to characterize the relationship between the administration and its employees. It is based on civil law, which once dominated administrative law (Al-Hadithi, 1975).

According to this theory, the employee occupies a contractual position governed by private law. The nature of the contract depends on the type of work performed. If the work is material, it is considered a

lease-of-services or employment contract. If legal in nature, it is considered an agency contract, with the employee's role limited to preparing or executing decisions without possessing any special powers (Tarsh, 2011).

This theory was dominant in French and Egyptian jurisprudence until the late 19th and 20th centuries (Mansour, 1969).

However, administrative jurists criticized this theory. Formally, a contract requires an offer followed by an identical acceptance by the other party. Such consent is absent in the appointment of public employees, as their appointment decision is not subject to their approval or rejection. Substantively, contracts governed by private law follow the principle that the contract binds both parties, meaning the administration could not alter the employee's legal status without their consent. In turn, this goes on to severely limit the government's ability to administer public services, since it.

2. The Adhesion Contract Theory Because of the criticisms directed towards the civil contract theory and because the civil contract theory could not be applicable in public services, there came into existence another theory—the theory of the adhesion contract. Here, the agreement between the state and the employee is seen as one where terms are predetermined by the administration, and the prospective employee merely accepts or rejects them without negotiation.

However, this theory was also criticized. Adhesion contracts typically apply to goods and services under monopoly conditions, which do not apply to public employment. Public office is not a commercial product but rather a public duty governed by strict criteria. Moreover, the (now-repealed) 1970 Iraqi Interim Constitution described public service as "a sacred trust and a social duty" (Article 1/3). Thus, applying the adhesion contract theory ignores essential aspects of public service, such as the non-negotiable nature of the employee's legal status.

3. The Public Law Contract Theory As administrative law evolved, particularly with the emergence of the French Conseil d'État and Egyptian administrative jurisprudence, a new theory emerged: the public law contract or contract of public employment.

The Egyptian judiciary, in a decision dated July 13, 1932, ruled that while the employee's relationship with the state begins contractually, it is a special type of contract governed by public law. These contracts grant the administration extensive powers to unilaterally modify terms in pursuit of the public interest, distinguishing them from civil law contracts (Mansour, 1969).

Nonetheless, this theory has also been criticized, particularly for limiting administrative flexibility due to the binding nature of contracts on both the administration and employees, and because any modification must adhere to specific conditions.

Second: Characterizing the Relationship as Organizational Contractual theories have faced widespread criticism for inadequately explaining the legal nature of public employment and for failing to ensure smooth functioning of public services due to the ambiguity in employee rights and obligations. Therefore, a prevailing view in modern jurisprudence is that the employee occupies an organizational position, not a contractual one (Jassim, 1979)

The relationship is governed by laws and regulations applicable to public service. Employees cannot object to this classification because their position is determined by law, under predefined terms and conditions before appointment. Such a legal arrangement ensures the smooth running of public utilities. The important implications of such a categorization include:

1. Employee consent is irrelevant to the legal effects of their appointment. Duties and responsibilities are predefined by law.
2. The employee holds an organizational position, and the administration may unilaterally modify public service rules at any time. The employee has no say in such modifications (Al-Ashmawi, 1959).

Any changes in service regulations apply to the employee without requiring consent—even if such changes result in termination, reduced pay, or increased responsibilities (Sorour, 1983).

3. Since the employee occupies an organizational position, the administration may not violate laws and regulations through mutual agreements with the employee. Any such agreement is null and void (Al-Malt, 1967).

4. Employees cannot strike or refuse to perform their duties, as this would disrupt essential public services. Such acts are considered serious breaches and, in some cases, criminal offenses.

Iraqi Penal Code No. 111 of 1969 (Article 364) stipulates:

"First: Any public employee or person assigned to public service who deliberately abandons their job—even under the guise of resignation—or refuses to perform a job-related duty, thereby endangering people's lives, health, or safety, or causing disruption or unrest, or disabling a public facility, shall be punished with imprisonment for up to two years, or a fine not exceeding 200 dinars, or both."

"Second: The penalty shall be aggravated if the offense is committed by three or more individuals in agreement or with a shared intent (Republic of Iraq, 1969)."

5. The organizational status of the employee obligates the administration to guarantee their rights. Resignation alone does not terminate employment; it must be formally accepted by the administration. Until then, the employee retains their status (Republic of Iraq, 1960).

Another view holds that the employee's status is purely organizational, not contractual, because the state unilaterally defines the legal framework regulating employment, including rights and duties. The state may alter these at any time, and such modifications cannot be contested as acquired rights—especially since salary and other benefits are subject to increase or decrease (Mahdi, 2022).

This organizational view was affirmed by Iraq's Supreme Administrative Court in Decision No. 168 / Employee Jurisdiction / Cassation / 2016, dated January 25, 2018: "The employee holds an organizational legal position (Republic of Iraq State Council, 2018)."

Egyptian jurisprudence has also settled on the view that the relationship between the administration and the employee is organizational in nature, governed by the laws and regulations of public service regarding appointment, service duration, rights, and duties.

The Impact of Privatization on the Legal Status of Public Employees

Privatization, as a process of transferring ownership or management of facilities or services from the public sector to the private sector, brings about profound transformations in the legal and regulatory structure governing the employment relationship of public employees. Its impact on those employees' legal status is marked by complexity and interrelatedness, influences across several planes, from the contractual to the in-depth constitutional rights and guarantees.

When privatization occurs, the legal nature of the relationship between the public employee and the state is revised. As a consequence of their position, public employees fall under particular legal systems often derived from the rules of administrative law that mark them as different from private employees due to the guarantees, discipline mechanisms, and legal protections they receive. With the transfer of a service or institution to the private sector, the employee may be moved to work within a commercial entity governed by ordinary labor law, resulting in the loss of many of the legal attributes previously associated with their status (Boualchouir, 2010).

One of the most significant changes that occurs is the loss of the statutory protection afforded to public employees. These employees often enjoy job stability that shields them from arbitrary dismissal and ensures levels of progression and disciplinary safeguards. In contrast, workers in the private sector—although protected by labor law—are more vulnerable to termination or changes in employment conditions, given the contractual nature of their relationship, which does not offer equivalent protection (Fahmy, 2000).

Privatization also raises the Issue of acquired rights. Public employees may have pension entitlements, bonuses, or benefits accumulated over years of service under the state's umbrella. These rights are often contested during the transition to privatized systems, as private companies, by default, are not obligated to provide or recognize the same entitlements unless explicitly regulated by transitional legal provisions (Bayna, 2011).

Transfer of Employees from the Public Sector to the Private Sector

The transfer of employees from the public sector to the private sector In Iraq represents one of the most significant legal and administrative transformations accompanying privatization processes or the restructuring of government institutions. This transition Is not merely seen as an individual movement, but rather as a shift In the legal nature of the employment relationship that previously existed between the employee and the state. Under Iraqi Civil Service Law No. 24 of 1960, the relationship between the employee and the state is regulated by statutory provisions that grant the employee a distinct legal status. This status Is closely linked to the functions of public service and entails various guarantees such as job security, disciplinary protection, administrative advancement, along with pension rights and benefits accrued through years of public service (Jawad, 2012).

When the state proceeds to privatize a public Institution or a specific activity, the legal status of employees working in that entity becomes a matter of concern. Questions arise regarding whether the employee will retain their employment status with the new private entity, whether they will be reassigned to another government institution, or whether they will be retired or offered a new employment contract under different terms. These questions often do not have a uniform answer, as Iraqi law does not explicitly provide a clear mechanism governing the transfer of public employees to the private sector within the context of privatization. Instead, such matters are frequently left to governmental administrative decisions or transitional agreements between the public body and the private sector (Al-Karkhi, 2014).

If an agreement Is reached to transfer the employee to the new entity, this effectively terminates their legal relationship with the state as a public servant and initiates a new relationship of a different nature governed by the provisions of Labor Law No. 37 of 2015. This law regulates the contractual relationship between the worker and the employer in the private sector. The shift carries significant Implications, most notably the loss of the legal guarantees associated with public employment, such as protection from dismissal except under strict conditions, and the structured systems of promotion and advancement typical In the public sector. Additionally, private institutions are not obligated to automatically recognize the acquired rights accumulated during the employee's public service unless such recognition Is explicitly included In clear agreements or binding transitional legal provisions (Al-Darraji, 2018).

First Branch: The Legal Status of Employees After Privatization

The legal status of the employee Is considered one of the most prominent features of distinction In administrative law, as It reflects the nature of the relationship between the state and the Individual within the framework of public service. In Iraq, the public employee enjoys, under the prevailing laws—chiefly the Civil Service Law No. 24 of 1960 and the State Employees Discipline Law—a legal status fundamentally different from that of a private sector worker. This legal status is not derived from a contract between two equal parties, as in labor contracts, but rather from an administrative decision Issued by an authorized body under the law. The employee is Integrated into the structure of public authority as an instrument for implementing government policies, committed to the principles of neutrality, public interest, and continuity (Abdullah, 2014).

However, this traditional conception of the employee's legal status began to weaken with the shift toward privatization policies, which gradually emerged in Iraq after 2003 as part of economic restructuring programs and due to pressures from International financial institutions. Privatization in Iraq has taken various forms, Including the complete liquidation of public institutions, converting them Into state-

owned companies preparing for sale, partnering with the private sector In management, or outsourcing public service provision (Khalil, 2016).

In this shift, however, the employee realizes that he or she finds himself at a “legal crossroads, fraught with ambiguity and risk.” As soon as, or indeed even before, the entity for which he or she works ceases being a public facility and becomes a private, for-profit enterprise, so too does the applicable law, including labor law, shift in accord with that status. The relationship no longer falls under the Civil Service Law but is instead regulated by the Labor Law No. 37 of 2015, which is based on the contractual balance between employer and worker, rather than on principles of public authority and administrative decisions (Mahmoud, 2012).

This shift in legal status encompasses several dimensions. First, the employee loses the status of “public employee” along with related legal privileges concerning job stability, disciplinary accountability governed by strict legal controls, and protection from dismissal except under legally specified conditions. Conversely, the worker becomes subject to market flexibility, where termination may be based on efficiency or profitability without a legal obligation to reassign or accommodate him in another position as in public service (Abdul Aziz, 2013).

Second, the retirement and social security systems differ significantly. The public employee is subject to a unified retirement system that considers years of service, base salary, and allowances, while the private sector worker is covered by the social security system, which is often less generous and more strictly tied to actual contributions paid. There is no legal guarantee obliging the new employer to recognize previous years of service unless explicitly stipulated in transfer agreements or temporary legislation, leading to the loss or delay of retirement rights (Hassan, 2017).

Third, the employee forfeits the right to administrative or judicial grievance procedures under the specialized administrative judiciary, which provides particular protection against administrative arbitrariness. Once transferred to the private sector, disputes fall under labor courts, which, while guaranteeing some basic worker rights, do not afford the same protections available to public employees. In terms of oversight mechanisms and substantive and procedural guarantees (Saeed, 2015).

The major problem in the Iraqi context lies in the absence of a clear, specific law regulating how to handle the employee’s legal status after privatization. No explicit legislation mandates the new entity to preserve the rights of transferred employees, regulate the calculation of previous service, or clarify standards ensuring a fair and balanced transfer respecting employee rights on one hand and economic efficiency considerations on the other. This legislative gap has allowed piecemeal approaches through ministerial decisions or temporary instructions that vary by sector and cause numerous legal disputes in courts (Youssef, 2011).

Practically, many employees transferred to privatized institutions or those managed in partnership with the private sector found themselves bound by new work contracts under inferior conditions without recognition of prior service or fair compensation. In some cases, they were not transferred at all but rather subjected to early retirement or dismissal without adequate guarantees. Some received financial compensation, but these solutions were not always equitable or governed by uniform standards (Abdullah, 2018).

In light of the foregoing, it can be said that the legal status of the Iraqi employee after privatization enters a gray legal zone requiring urgent legislative intervention to establish fixed rules governing employment transitions, protecting acquired rights, and balancing economic privatization demands with social and employment justice. A law or at least an executive regulation should be drafted explicitly addressing the status of employees transferred after privatization, specifying how to calculate previous service, guaranteeing non-diminution of retirement rights, setting clear dispute resolution mechanisms, and preventing the new employer’s arbitrary contract renewals or dismissals. Without this legislative framework, the employee’s legal status after privatization will remain subject to discretion, inconsistency, and selectivity, incompatible with justice principles and good administrative reform requirements (Mustafa, 2014).

Second Branch: Legal Guarantees for Employees During the Transition

The Legal Guarantees for Public Employees Transitioning to the Private Sector.

The functional transition of public employees to non-governmental entities, or their Institutional shift from the public sector to the private sector, represents one of the most complex situations within the legal and administrative system. In such cases, there arises an urgent need for clear legal safeguards that maintain a balance between the state's interest in modernization and efficiency enhancement, and the employee's right to job stability and protection from harm resulting from changes over which they have no control. These transitions, often marked by legal ambiguity, disruption of acquired rights, and limited possibilities of objection or appeal, are fundamentally making legal guarantees very important to ensure legitimacy and justice (Al-Obaidi, 2010).

As a tool that organizes social and administrative relationships, the law intervenes to regulate the rhythm of this transition through a set of principles and provisions Intended to preserve the legal status of the employee. At the forefront of these guarantees Is the principle of "non-violation of acquired rights"—a well-established rule in both legal theory and administrative jurisprudence. This principle asserts that rights acquired under existing laws cannot be diminished or revoked except through legislation, and any job transition must not result in the reduction or circumvention of these rights, whether related to salary, promotion, or retirement (Abdul Rahman, 2013).

From another angle, the Issue of the legality of changes in the legal framework governing the employment relationship Is raised. Before the transition, a public employee Is subject to civil service laws or other public employment regulations, which grant them a special status as part of the public authority, not merely a worker receiving wages for services. This status changes entirely post-transition, where the employment relationship usually falls under labor law—a contractual framework that ostensibly balances the relationship between employee and employer, but practically lacks many of the protections afforded to public employees, such as stringent disciplinary safeguards, the right to file complaints with administrative or judicial bodies, and job stability not linked to performance or profit (Al-Zaidi, 2017).

In light of this transformation, there arises a dual need for protection: on one hand, protection from dismissal, discrimination, or exclusion during the transition process; and on the other hand, protection from the reduction of benefits or the loss of acquired rights without fair compensation. Hence, the Importance of establishing explicit and binding transitional rules that regulate how employees are transferred and define their legal status—whether they remain In service, are reassigned to another role, are retired with compensation, or are rehired under new terms without undermining their rights (Ali, 2012).

The absence or weakness of such rules leaves the employee In a legal vacuum—no longer protected by the safeguards of public employment, yet not fully covered by labor law provisions, particularly amid the imbalance of power between the worker and the new private institution (Abdul Sattar, 2011). This situation raises questions about the extent to which the principles of equality and equal opportunity are respected, and exposes administrative transition to legal risks and potential social unrest (Abdul Karim, 2015).

Legal guarantees are not confined to the substance of legal texts, but also include the procedures through which the transition takes place. The employee must be an active party in this process and not merely the object. This means the employee must be taken into confidence in the decision-making process itself and informed of all aspects of the transfer, have the right to protest the transfer, and be permitted to state his point of view in front of grievance committees and through proper courts of law. In addition, the body to which the employee is transferred must be prepared to keep intact his rights and compensate him in an appropriate manner and be amenable to judicial review (Karim, 2014).

And what can most effectively strengthen these protections is, of course, clear legislative intervention. Only law has the power of imposition of balance within an unbalanced relationship—and especially within a relationship wherein the receiving organization is for-profit and does not cherish the traditional

ideals of public service. In many comparative systems, such as France, specific legislation is enacted to regulate employee transitions post-privatization. These laws ensure the inclusion of previous service years, continued pension rights, and the possibility of returning to public service under specific conditions, while also placing strict limitations on the new employer regarding contract termination or unilateral changes without valid justification (Yassin, 2016).

In Iraq, however, this field still suffers from clear legislative shortcomings. There is no unified law regulating the transition of public employees to the private sector or addressing their status after institutional privatization. Most cases are handled through partial administrative decisions or ministerial instructions, which often lack legal force or are applied selectively. This reality allows for broad discretionary interpretation and may result in employees losing their rights or being treated as redundant, thus stripping the privatization project of its developmental essence and turning it into a vehicle for job elimination rather than institutional reform (Hameed, 2018).

Legal guarantees, therefore, are not just rigid legal concepts—they are a social, political, and economic necessity, representing the minimum protection against radical transformations. If these guarantees are not codified in clear and binding provisions, they will remain mere slogans with no real-world application, and employees' rights will remain under threat in every organizational or economic shift (Mohamed, 2019).

Legal and Social Challenges Resulting from the Privatization of Public Service

The privatization of public employment represents a profound transformation in the structure of the state and its social function, whereby some or all of the jobs and services previously managed directly by the state are transferred to the private sector. All these mean that this change is not a different way of managing and handling issues, or a way of trying to enhance economic efficiency, but rather a radical redefinition of this public service relationship between the state and the citizen, between the public sector employee and their professional status. All these give a whole variety of legal and very complex issues which seem hard to dissociate within the political and economic framework within which this change is taking place (Al-Fadli, 2011).

From a legal perspective, the problems and challenges mostly reside in addressing the legal status of the public sector employee after the institution where they render their services gets privatized. The public sector employee enjoys a special status, which is regulated by civil service legislation, that provides these employees with rights which are not granted to workers in the private sector, such as the right not to be arbitrarily dismissed, promotion according to certain criteria, and having a fixed retirement program. After a public sector employee gets a new employer who is from the private sector, this employee stands to lose a considerable number of rights, especially in the absence of a transitional legislation framework (Al-Rifai, 2014).

Moreover, there arises a legal inconclusiveness with regard to the new legal order governing the employment contract. The new employee, who is bound by public service legislation, is now governed by legislation related to labor, which is premised on logic concerning adaptability or contracting. This therefore implies that the guaranteed protection such a person received is now open to negotiation, depending on the balance of power between such an individual as well as the new employer. Indeed, there are not insignificant concerns with regard to equality of treatment as discrepancies may arise between those who remain within public service among those who transition to private enterprise (Al-Saadi, 2016).

Looking from a social point of view, the impact of privatization is clear, especially concerning the professional and psychological stability of workers. Lack of job security leads to a sense of anxiety, thereby undermining the professional's capacity to plan or make provisions concerning his or her personal as well as professional life. In addition to this, those who perceive exclusion or redundancy may

consider privatization as a tool, especially if there is already a pronounced sense of unemployment or lack of adequate social protection (Al-Dulaimi, 2012).

The shift from a public function tied to national service and public responsibility to a private role evaluated on the basis of profit and productivity may lead to changes in professional and ethical values. The public employee, once seen as a representative of public authority and a provider of citizen services, may become a mere worker striving to meet the financial goals of a private company. This shift in professional identity may lower ethical and social engagement with the public interest and the feeling of belonging to the Institution and the nation.

There is also an important social issue linked to distributive justice. When privatization is implemented, it can create a situation where certain employees are retained on the basis of their skill sets, leaving other skill sets open to exclusion. It widens the gap between employees on the socioeconomic scale. In addition, the government might be left with less control over the sector because of the fact that the state's guarantee of equality of opportunity might not remain uniform if the sector is privatized (Al-Sharif, 2015).

It should be noted that the lack of tools for transparency and accountability within the process of privatization contributes to these challenges. The fact is that the process of privatization takes place within an administrative setting that faces challenges related to corruption and a lack of oversight, thus paving the way for the manipulation of contracts and the abuse of influence as well as the violation of rights for both employees and citizens. As such, the process of privatization ceases to be an effective means for improvement and instead helps to entrench inequality within the public employment system (Al-Janabi, 2010).

In conclusion, privatization is not just an economic decision; it is a legal, social, and highly political one. It requires an integrated approach that takes into consideration not only the question of financial feasibility but also their impact on individual rights and the social contract between the state and its citizens. The lack of balance in the management of this change undermines confidence in the institutions and weakens national belonging, while privatization seems to be more of a burden than an opportunity for reform (Al-Zaidi, 2018).

First Branch: The Compatibility of Privatization with the Principle of Public Service Stability

Stability of public employment principle

The stability of public employment principle is viewed as one of the basic pillars upon which the legal and administrative system within Iraq rests. This principle represents a universal vision concerning the position of the public employee as a holder of a position which goes beyond temporary work into a relatively permanent relationship between the individual and the state. This relationship is based on guaranteeing job rights and job security. Stability of public employment in Iraqi law is closely linked to the philosophy of public service, which aims to protect the employee from any arbitrary decisions that may harm his job status, while providing an environment that enables him to perform his duties with confidence and psychological security, thereby achieving the state's goals in delivering public services efficiently and fairly (Hassan, 2012).

However, privatization, as a recent phenomenon that has strongly entered the Iraqi scene over the last two decades, represents a fundamental challenge to this principle. Privatization is the process by which the administration of some sectors or services is transferred from a public to a private entity, which imposes a new logic that is characterized by flexibility in the economic sphere, economic efficiency, and less burden on the state. In this context, employment in the private sector is viewed as a temporary contractual relationship based on profit and efficiency, not as a permanent institutional relationship grounded in stability and job guarantees. This change in the nature of employment creates a clear contradiction with the firmly established legal principle in Iraq that grants public employees strong

guarantees, such as protection from arbitrary dismissal and the enjoyment of retirement rights and regular promotions (Hussein, 2014).

From a legal perspective, this contradiction becomes clear when privatization is applied without a clear legislative framework defining how to handle the status of the public employee who is transferred from the governmental sector to the private sector. Although Iraqi law contains regulatory provisions protecting the public employee, these provisions are often insufficient or not fully enforced in cases of privatization. There are no clear transitional rules protecting the employee's rights, such as ensuring salary continuity, counting previous years of service, or even providing the right to appeal or review if exposed to dismissal or reduction of benefits. This legal void leaves the employee in a vulnerable position, where he may easily lose acquired rights and become subject to discrimination or exclusion in the private labor market (Abdullah, 2016).

On the social side, the loss of stability in public employment directly affects the psychological and social condition of employees. Job stability is not limited to financial aspects but also extends to the sense of security and reassurance that enables the employee to plan for his professional and family future. When this stability is disrupted due to privatization measures that may lay off employees or reduce their benefits, anxiety and mistrust spread among workers, negatively affecting their performance and morale within institutions. This situation also increases fears of job loss, especially in a country like Iraq suffering from high unemployment rates and weak social protection systems, making privatization fraught with social and political risks (Hassan, 2011).

Privatization also affects the professional identity of the public employee. The employee, who was once viewed as a servant of the public interest responsible for providing excellent service to citizens, gradually transforms into just an employee in a private institution, where his value is measured by performance and profitability rather than service to society. This transformation weakens the sense of belonging and loyalty to the institution and creates a gap between the employee and the state, which may reflect negatively on the quality of services provided and on the institutional capacity of the state in the long run (Mahmoud, 2013).

Moreover, the absence of transitional laws regulating privatization exacerbates this problem, as the process is often conducted arbitrarily or through partial administrative decisions that do not consider employees' rights nor provide clear alternatives. This situation allows for abuses such as arbitrary dismissal or forced retirement without appropriate compensation, or transferring the employee to an entity that does not provide the same job guarantees. What worsens the situation is that the new private sector may not be subject to the same standards and controls that governed the public sector, thus opening the door to deterioration in working conditions and a decline in legal protection (Abdullah, 2015).

Therefore, the greatest challenge facing the Iraqi legal system lies in how to achieve a balance between the requirements of privatization, which aims to modernize the economy and improve administrative efficiency, and preserving the principle of stability of public employment, which is the cornerstone for protecting employee rights and ensuring the continuity of high-quality public services. Without a clear legislative and regulatory framework, this balance suffers, resulting in a decline in employees' trust in the state and its ability to manage its human resources fairly and sustainably (Youssef, 2017).

Hence, there is an urgent need to draft clear laws regulating the privatization of public jobs and ensuring a smooth and fair transition for employees, so they do not lose their acquired rights nor are deprived of the legal protection they enjoyed in the public sector. This framework should include guarantees for continuity of rights, fair compensation mechanisms, transparent procedures that allow employees to participate in transition decisions, and judicial and administrative oversight ensuring the effective implementation of these guarantees (Abdul Karim, 2010).

In conclusion, the compatibility of privatization with the principle of stability of public employment in Iraqi law can only be achieved through comprehensive development of the legal and administrative system, integrating the requirements of economic development with social and legal obligations toward

employees. Job stability is not an obstacle to change but a necessary guarantee for achieving genuine reform and institutional effectiveness, preserving the state's essential role in regulating employment relations and protecting the rights of employees and citizens alike (Mohammed, 2018).

Second Branch: Legal Protection Amid the Absence of Sufficient Legislative Guarantees

Legal protection is the backbone in every legal and administrative system. Legal protection preserves the rights of Individuals, specifically employees and workers, both in the public and private sectors, from any sort of abuses or arbitrariness that could lead to harming their Interests and professional lives in the future. The lack or insufficiency of legislation that provides such legal protection in Iraq illustrates a number of issues stemming from the weakness of the justice system and human rights protection within the working environment. Such a lack in legislation not only comes from the absence of laws but also from the lack of enforcement by the administration, which does not have the necessary capability or will to enforce such laws effectively (Al-Taie, 2013).

First, it can be argued that a lack of legislation or the presence of inappropriate and contradictory laws brings about a situation of confusion and uncertainty as far as the relationship and duties of the parties are concerned, placing the employee in a situation of uncertainty and insecurity in relation to their employment relationship. In instances where the law is not clearly defined in relation to the rights and responsibilities of the affected employee, the administrative body can take advantage of the same and make decisions that are arbitrarily expressed through wrongful termination of employment, reduction of salaries, among others (Al-Ali, 2016).

All these decisions often find employees with few choices or even mechanisms of defense because of the absence of legislative measures set up to protect them against these practices. Moreover, the absence of specific legislation concerning complaint mechanisms and legal appeals is seen as the most significant barrier for employees in defending their rights. The inability of legislation to guarantee the right of grievance filing and to ensure fair and transparent procedures for assessing employment disputes deprives workers of access to justice and makes them susceptible to arbitrary administrative decisions. This is also a limitation to the possibility of judicial or administrative bodies checking administrative performance and rectifying violations, weakening respect for employee rights and encouraging administrative despotism (Al-Jubouri, 2015).

From a social point of view, this fragile legal environment creates an atmosphere of distrust and continuous tension among employees. It is human nature that in order to do their job with dignity and care, they have to get a sense of security. When this sense is absent, their performance goes worse, enthusiasm for institutional loyalty shrinks, and professional and ethical values weaken. In Iraq, which has serious problems in its labor market, such as high unemployment rates, the lack of legal protection creates additional psychological and social pressure, boosting tension and unrest among workers and threatening general social stability (Mohammed, 2014).

Additionally, the absence of protective laws perpetuates corruption and nepotism, in which some officials take advantage of weaknesses in the laws in order to lay down unjust terms or fire some employees for subjective reasons. This does not only cause harm to the involved employees but also contributes towards the poor performance of the administration, as well as the performance of the provided services to the citizens (Khalil, 2012).

Conversely, building a comprehensive legal protection scheme also needs more than the enactment of new legislation. This legislation also needs to be comprehensive, entailing all legal aspects of the employment relationship, from hiring to rights and obligations, and then from termination to retirement as well as grievance procedures. In addition, this should be accompanied by the development of effective, supervisory, and legal institutions having Independence and ensuring the effective implementation of the legislation. In addition, there also has to be created a legal awareness level among administrators as well

as workers regarding their respective rights and obligations in order to take advantage of the legal schemes available to them (Hassan, 2017).

With a view to these requirements, the Iraq country lacks any kind of legal safeguard against these issues, which constitute a significant barrier towards realizing social justice and employment security, blocking the way towards developmental restructuring. Without filling this void through the formulation of comprehensive legislation along with effective means of enforcing it, it will remain weak in terms of safeguarding workers against arbitrary dismissal or dismissal at any time without any recourse at all (Saleh, 2018).

In conclusion, it is therefore conclusive that adequate legal protection is largely based on a strong legislative system which safeguards workers' rights and provides them with mechanisms to protect their rights, and this is based on a strong monitoring system of judicial and administrative authorities. Without this system in Iraqi law, workers are at a high risk that endangers their right and security at work, which has an effect on public administration and services delivered by this state. Hence, this problem should be at the top of any state of law that is proposed as a result of administrative reform (Saeed, 2011).

Conclusion

This research has proved the existence of deep legal implications of the privatization policy in Iraq as a strategic method of economic transformation in the state, which threatens the essence of the functional relationship between the Iraqi state and public employees. There is a clear point of view according to which the aim of the policy of privatization is the promotion of administrative and financial efficiency in public sectors. Nevertheless, the reality is the opposite because the policy of privatization jeopardizes the principle of job stability and the rights of public employees in the context of the lacking legal protection of the employees in the absence of appropriate legal mechanisms for the transfer and protection of these employees in the context of the policy of privatization.

Findings

1. Privatization within the Iraqi State has, in many cases, been carried out in the absence of a legal framework to cover the relationship between public sector workers and their new employer, resulting in direct and indirect violations of their rights.
2. Under current Iraq law, the following are insufficient to protect public service workers against the implications of privatization, especially where there is unjustified transfer or termination of service:
3. There is an evident weakness in the ability to activate the judicial/administrative process to protect the right to appeal or obtain compensation for unjust treatment/dismissals.
4. The lack of legal knowledge amongst the majority of the workforce has denied the employees an opportunity to know their rights and assert those rights through legal channels.

Recommendations

1. Passage of specific legislation that will cover the regulation of the privatization process, including the transition of public sector employees, their rights, obligations before, during, and after the institutional transformation.
2. Improved legal protection for affected employees in the event of privatization decisions, such as the regulation of arbitrary dismissal and the award of proper compensation.
3. Ensure the role of administrative courts and oversight bodies in ensuring the promotion of the rights of employees.
4. The creation of a national compensation fund for employees who find their services terminated on account of privatization where no effective alternative employment exists.

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